

Spectrophotometric Determination of Pharmaceutically Important Primary Arylamines with Metol and NBS

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Metol in the presence of N-bromosuccinimide (NBS) is proposed as a new reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of microgram amounts of pharmaceutically important primary arylamines. The resulting purple-red species exhibit maximum absorbance at 520-530 nm. Beer's law limits, molar absorptivity, the effects of time, order of addition of reagents, reagent concentration and interference studies are reported.

N-BROMOSUCCINIMIDE (NBS) has been used so far as a titrimetric reagent in the determination of pharmaceutically important primary arylamines¹⁻⁵ due to its rapid bromination reaction. In continuation of our investigations on the spectrophotometric determination of several primary arylamines using metol (P-N-methylamino phenol sulphate) in the presence of an oxidizing agent⁶⁻⁸, the analytical determination using metol and NBS is reported here. It is based on our observation that metol gives purple-red colour (λ_{max} 520-530 nm) with NBS at pH 3.1±0.1 only in the presence of primary arylamine, and that the intensity of the colour is directly proportional to the concentration of primary arylamine initially taken. The method has been employed for the determination of pharmaceutically important primary arylamines such as sulpha drugs, local anaesthetics and dapsone.

Experimental

Instrumentation: Spectral and absorbance measurements were made with Beckmann (DB-G) double beam spectrophotometer with 1 cm matched glass cells. Elico model LI-120 Digital pH-meter was used for pH measurements.

Reagents: All solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water. A freshly prepared 0.2% aqueous solution of metol was always used.

A solution of NBS (0.02 M) was freshly prepared and its strength was ascertained by the arsenite method⁹. Mercuric acetate (0.01 M) and potassium bromide (0.01M) solutions were prepared in the usual way.

Buffer solutions: Potassium acidphthalate-hydrochloric acid buffer solutions (pH 2.2-3.7) were prepared as described by Lurie¹⁰.

Primary arylamines: All the pharmaceutically important primary arylamines were commercially available - G.R., I.P. or B.P. grade. Their stock solutions were prepared in distilled water, the compounds insoluble in water being dissolved initially in the minimum amount of dilute hydrochloric acid or sodium hydroxide solution if necessary. Working

solutions were prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock solutions after neutralisation of the excess acid or alkali. The pH of the final diluted solution was in the range 6.0-8.0. All the other reagents used, were of analytical grade.

General procedure: 15 ml of 0.3% acetic acid or potassium acidphthalate buffer (pH 3.1±0.05), 1 ml of 0.018M NBS and 2 ml of 0.2% metol solutions were successively placed in a 25 ml volumetric flask. A 1.0-5.0 ml portion of primary arylamine (concentration range as indicated in Table 1) and requisite volume of distilled water were added so as

TABLE 1—ASSAY OF PHARMACEUTICAL PRIMARY ARYLAMINES

Sl. No.	Amine	Beer's law limits ($\mu\text{g}/25\text{ ml}$)	Molar absorptivity $\times 10^{-3}, 1\text{ mol}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$	% Recovery	Standard deviation
1.	Aniline	100-400	1.75	98.9	0.03
2.	<i>o</i> -Toluidine	200-450	1.1	99.1	0.042
3.	<i>p</i> -Toluidine	300-450	0.8	99.2	0.025
4.	Sulphanilic acid	50-850	7.1	99.6	0.008
5.	Sulphaguanidine	50-550	6.4	99.8	0.004
6.	Sulphasomidine	50-550	6.8	99.6	0.005
7.	Sulphadimidine	50-500	6.95	99.7	0.007
8.	Sulphacetamide	50-450	6.8	99.5	0.038
9.	Sulphadiazine	50-500	6.5	99.4	0.029
10.	Sulphapyridine	50-500	6.48	99.8	0.004
11.	Sulphamoxole	50-550	6.4	99.6	0.005
12.	Sulphamerazine	50-550	6.65	99.7	0.014
13.	Sulphamethoxazole	50-300	6.5	100.2	0.008
14.	Sulphafurazole	50-450	6.75	100.4	0.013
15.	Sulphathiazole	50-400	7.25	99.4	0.018
16.	Sulphamethoxy pyridiazine	100-600	6.6	99.6	0.009
17.	<i>p</i> -Amino benzoic acid (PABA)	50-300	6.85	99.7	0.007
18.	Benzoaine	50-300	7.5	99.4	0.021
19.	Procaine hydrochloride	50-400	7.2	99.6	0.007
20.	Dapsone	50-350	12.5	99.8	0.016
21.	Chloramphenicol*	200-600	4.0	98.8	0.056
22.	Folic acid*†	200-650	5.9	98.6	0.061

* After carrying out reduction.

† Applying suitable correction for free amine and using PABA as standard.

to make the total volume 25 ml. The absorbance was measured at 530 nm after 20 min against a reagent blank prepared in a similar manner. The primary amine concentration was read from a standard calibration curve prepared with the same compound under identical conditions.

Procedure to compound which yield primary arylamino group on reduction: About 10 mg of sample was accurately weighed and treated with 10 ml of dilute hydrochloric acid and 0.25 g of zinc dust added in portions. After standing for 1 hr at room temperature, the solution was filtered through cotton wool, the residue was washed with three 5 ml portions of water and the filtrate was brought to pH 3.0 with sodium hydroxide and diluted to 100 ml in a standard flask. The general procedure was then applied.

Procedure for pharmaceutical preparations: The sampling and preliminary treatment of pharmaceutical preparations such as tablets, injection and eye drops were performed according to the reported procedures^{11,12} before carrying out the assay with the general procedure.

Results and Discussion

Absorbance curves: The absorbance curves of all pharmaceutically important primary arylamines show maximum absorbance at 520-530 nm, where as metol-NBS or primary arylamines-NBS has practically no absorption.

Effect of pH: Maximum colour development takes place in the pH range 2.9-3.2. All studies are therefore confined to pH 3.1 ± 0.05 using acetic acid or potassium acidphthalate buffer.

Effect of order of addition: The order of mixing buffer (B), NBS (N), metol (M) and primary arylamine (P) has some effect on the development of colour. Maximum colour development takes place in 20 minutes when the order of mixing BNMP is carried out within 2 minutes. Incomplete colour development takes place either making delay in the same order of addition or changing the order of addition (BPMN, BMPN or BPNM).

Effect of metol concentration: 2 ml of 0.2% metol solution is required for the maximum colour development. Higher concentration of metol (upto 4 ml of 0.2%) does not alter the colour intensity.

Effect of NBS concentration: The concentration of NBS is highly critical. Maximum colour is developed when 0.8-1.2 ml of 0.018M NBS is used. Complete disappearance of colour is noticed when 1.8 ml or more of 0.018M NBS is used.

Effects of mercuric acetate and potassium bromide: The influence of 1 ml each of 0.01M solutions of mercuric acetate and potassium bromide on the colour development under experimental conditions has been studied. Mercuric acetate lowers the colour intensity to $\frac{2}{3}$ and potassium bromide enhances the colour intensity to $\frac{7}{8}$ times of the original colour. These studies reveal

that the oxidation of metol with NBS in the presence of primary arylamine (PABA) takes place via molecular bromine¹³.

Effect of ion exchange resin: The cationic nature of the complex is indicated by the retention of the purple-red colour on IR-50 cation exchange resin.

Beer's law limits, molar absorptivity values, % recoveries and standard deviation using the absorbance of eight solutions containing 300 μg of primary arylamine are included in Table 1. The values obtained by the proposed and Bratton-Marshall method¹¹ for pharmaceutical preparations are compared in Table 2.

TABLE 2—ASSAY OF PHARMACEUTICAL PRIMARY ARYL AMINES IN DOSAGE FORMS

Dosage form	Nominal Content (g)	Found, g	
		Proposed method	Bratton-Marshall method
<i>Tablets</i>			
Sulphaguanidine	0.500	0.494	0.497
Sulphadimidine	0.500	0.495	0.498
Sulphapyridine	0.500	0.492	0.488
Sulphosomidine	0.500	0.504	0.501
Sulphamoxole	0.500	0.502	0.495
Dapsona	0.025	0.0241	0.0244
Folic acid	0.005	0.0046	0.0047
<i>Capsules</i>			
Chloramphenicol	0.250	0.246	0.248
<i>Eye-drops and Injections</i>			
Albucid-sulphacetamide sodium	1.420	1.38	1.35
Sulphadiazine	1.000	0.96	0.98

Interferences: The following amounts (ppm) of other constituents usually present in pharmaceutical preparations are found to give less than 3% error in the determination of 18 ppm primary arylamine (e.g. sulphacetamide) talc (400), magnesium stearate (400), calcium phosphate (250), sodium chloride (500), chloramphenicol (300), penicillins (300), tetracyclines (100), streptomycin (150), glucose (940), lactose (50) and trimethoprim (100).

Mechanism: The spectrum of the coloured species of metol with NBS, iodine or chromium(VI) in the presence of primary arylamine (e.g. PABA) at pH 3.0 has been found to have an absorption maximum at 520-530 nm and exhibit molar absorptivity $7.1 \pm 0.3 \times 10^5 \text{ lit mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The maximum intensity of the colour is developed within 15 minutes and is stable for 2 hrs. The spectrum of the oxidation product of metol, P-N-methylbenzoquinoneimine, which forms on treating metol with chromium(VI) or iodine monochloride at pH 6-8 also possesses the same absorption maximum (λ_{max} 520-530 nm) but the absorbance very slowly increases with time and fades even before reaching maximum intensity observed in the previous case. These studies reveal that the stable coloured species

are originating from P-N-methylbenzoquinoneimine [formed *in situ* with metol and iodine, NBS or chromium(VI) and primary arylamine]. The composition of the coloured species formed between P-N-methylbenzoquinoneimine and primary arylamine (e.g. PABA) was determined spectrophotometrically using three, molar ratio¹⁴, Job's continuous variation¹⁵ and slope ratio¹⁶ methods. These methods show that P-N-methylbenzoquinoneimine and primary arylamine combine in a 2 : 1 molar ratio. In the case of Dapsone (possesses two primary arylamino groups), the molar ratio of the coloured species has been found to be 4 : 1 indicating the involvement of two P-N-methylbenzoquinoneimine molecules for each primary arylamino group.

From the results presented in Table 1, it appears that the effects (inductive, mesomeric and steric) of substituents in the positions ortho, meta and para to the amino group of aniline lead to marked variation in molar absorptivity values, even though the absorption maximum and the molar ratio of the coloured complex remains the same. It can be seen that the molar absorptivity values of primary arylamines in the presence of the electron-withdrawing groups ($-\text{SO}_2\text{H}$, $-\text{SO}_2\text{NH}_2$, $-\text{SO}_2\text{NHR}$, $-\text{COOH}$, $-\text{COOR}$ and $-\text{COCH}_3$) are higher than those containing electron releasing groups ($-\text{CH}_3$).

From the above results the complex may be regarded as a weak charge transfer type. The charge transfer may be presumed to be taking place involving electron transfer from the highest occupied π molecular orbital of primary arylamine (PABA) to the lowest empty molecular orbitals of the two adjacent P-N-methylbenzoquinoneimine molecules. The two P-N-methylbenzoquinoneimine molecules are being probably brought closer by primary arylamine through hydrogen bonding thus facilitating the simultaneous overlap of the π molecular orbital of PABA with the π^* orbitals of the two P-N-methylbenzoquinoneimine molecules as shown below. The high molar absorptivity values of primary arylamines with electron withdrawing group (e.g. PABA ; $\text{R}=\text{COOH}$) may be due to the enhancement of π complex forming ability of the phenyl ring through the delocalization of nonbonding electrons on nitrogen of amino group¹⁷.

Similar overlapping of the π - π^* orbitals were reported in the 1 : 1 CT complex formed between chloranil and N, N, N¹, N¹-tetramethyl-p-phenylene diamine¹⁸.

The proposed mechanism is substantiated by the fact that the molecular complex is not extractable

by organic solvents but is adsorbed by cation exchange resin. The very low molar absorptivity values of the secondaryamine (N-methylaniline : molar absorptivity value 0.4×10^8 lit mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) and tertiary amine (N, N-dimethylaniline : molar absorptivity 0.09×10^8 lit mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) may be due to the possibility of 1 : 1 hydrogen bonding between donor and acceptor and the total absence of hydrogen bonding respectively.

It has been found, that variation of NBS to higher concentrations in the present procedure, leads to complete disappearance of colour. To know the influence of NBS in the formation of coloured species, the following titrimetric procedures were carried out. The consumption of NBS (when 1 ml of 0.018 M was used, the concentration suitable for maximum colour development) under experimental conditions in the case of metol (2 ml, 0.2%), PABA (1 ml, 0.103%) and mixture of metol (2 ml, 0.2%), and PABA (1 ml, 0.03%) was determined separately using the arsenite method to titrate the excess NBS. This study revealed that one mole of metol in the presence and absence of PABA consumes 1.45 moles of NBS, even though 1 mole of PABA consumes 3.3 moles of NBS. Similar studies using higher concentration of NBS (2 ml of 0.018M; the concentration favourable for complete disappearance of colour) indicating that the consumption of NBS in the case of metol, metol in the presence of PABA and PABA is respectively 2.41, 2.76 and 3.4 moles. Metol requires 2.0 moles of NBS for complete conversion to its oxidation product, P-N-methylbenzoquinoneimine which being unstable undergoes hydrolysis leading to the formation of *p*-benzoquinone and methylamine. These studies suggest that the bromination of primary arylamine takes place only after the complete conversion of metol to P-N-methylbenzoquinoneimine. The colour development may be due to the involvement of unsubstituted primary arylamine (PABA) and not its bromo substituted derivative (steric hindrance) in the molecular complex. The effect of order of mixing supports this proposition.

This method offers a simple, accurate and sensitive spectrophotometric method for the estimation of pharmaceutical primary arylamines.

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References

1. R. D. TIWARI and J. P. SHARMA and I. C. SHUKLA, *Talanta*, 1967, 14, 853.
2. M. Z. BARAKAT, A. S. FAYZALLA, EL-AASSAR, M. SHAKER, *Microchem. J.*, 1979, 18, 309.

3. M. Z. BARAKAT and M. SHAKER, *Analyst*, 1964, **89**, 216.
4. M. SHAKER and G. W. YOUSSEF, *Microchem. J.*, 1974, **19**, 339.
5. M. GOPAL and U. C. PANDE, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1975, **277**, 125.
6. R. R. KRISHNA and C. S. P. SASTRY, *Talanta*, 1979, **26**, 861.
7. R. R. KRISHNA, P. SIRAJ and C. S. P. SASTRY, *Ind. J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1979, **41**, 200.
8. R. R. KRISHNA, P. SIRAJ and C. S. P. SASTRY, *Acta Ciencia Indica*, (in press).
9. M. Z. BARAKAT and M. F. ABT EL-WAHAB, *Anal. Chem.*, 1954, **26**, 1973.
10. JU. LURIE, *Hand-Book of Analytical Chemistry*, MIR publishers, Moscow, 1975, 255.
11. A. C. BRATTON and E. K. MARSHALL, JR., *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1939, **128**, 537.
12. M. M. AMER and M. I. WALASH, *Bull. Fac. Pharm., Cairo, Cairo Univ.*, 1973, **2**, 161.
13. N. VENKATA SUBRAMANYAN and V. THIAGARAJAN, *Tet. Lett.*, 1967, **35**, 3349.
14. J. H. YOE and A. L. JONES, *Analyst*, 1944, **16**, 111.
15. P. JOB, *Ann. Chem.*, 1928, **9**, 113.
16. A. E. HARVEY and D. L. MANNING, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4488.
17. B. B. WAYLAND and R. S. DRAGO, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **86**, 5240.
18. R. FOSTER and T. J. THOMPSON, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1962, **58**, 860.